

RemNavi State of Remote Hiring

2026 H1: Salary Disclosure, Remote Quality, and EU Pay Transparency Directive Readiness

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Abstract

This report presents the first half-year 2026 snapshot of the RemNavi remote-job corpus, focused on salary disclosure rates, remote-quality scoring distribution, employer transparency behaviour, and a forward-looking readiness signal ahead of the EU Pay Transparency Directive (Directive (EU) 2023/970), which takes effect on 7 June 2026. The analysis covers 8,844 active remote job listings aggregated from all the major remote-job boards and ATS career-page feeds during the May 2026 snapshot window. Of these, 1,897 listings (21.4%) carry a verifiable numeric salary range; 3,410 listings carry a composite Real Remote Score on a public 100-point five-pillar rubric. The disclosed median remote salary is \$207,000/year (P25 \$154,500; P75 \$257,000). Only 3.0% of scored listings reach the Strong tier (60–80) or above; 48.2% sit in the Weak tier (0–20). The middle of the score distribution is thin, suggesting a polarised market in which listings tend to either disclose substantively or not at all. 1,320 Europe-region listings (14.9% of corpus) are the population to which the EU Pay Transparency Directive most directly applies; the directive is expected to compress this share's disclosure gap over the next two quarters. The underlying dataset is published under CC BY 4.0 at remnavi.com/data_export.php; the methodology version applied to all figures in this report is RRS v1 (Zenodo DOI 10.5281/zenodo.20234690).

Keywords: remote work; remote hiring; salary transparency; EU Pay Transparency Directive; Real Remote Score; transparency-scored remote jobs; labour-market measurement; open data; CC BY 4.0.

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1. Introduction

This report presents the first H1 2026 snapshot of the RemNavi corpus, intended as a citable reference for researchers, journalists, regulators, and data scientists working on the remote labour market in connection with the EU Pay Transparency Directive (Directive (EU) 2023/970), the broader US state pay-transparency regulatory landscape (notably California Assembly Bill 2282, Colorado SB 19-085, New York Local Law 32, Washington SB 5761), and the structural transformation of remote hiring practices through 2025–2026.

The figures in this report were extracted from live RemNavi API endpoints at the snapshot date stated on the title page. Every figure is reproducible from the live endpoints listed in §11, in the methodology version listed in the suggested citation. Subsequent revisions of this report will be deposited as new versions of the present Zenodo record; the underlying methodology is published separately at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20234690>.

2. Methodology and data sources

The full methodology – source inventory, ingestion cadence, deduplication, salary treatment, Real Remote Score and Hybrid Transparency Score rubrics, scope and limitations – is described in RemNavi (2026), RemNavi Remote Job Market Methodology, Version 1.0, Zenodo DOI 10.5281/zenodo.20234690 (see §13 References). This report applies that methodology to the May 2026 corpus snapshot and presents the resulting H1 findings.

2.1 The Real Remote Score rubric

The RRS is a 0–100 composite measuring how genuinely remote a listing is. Five weighted pillars, fixed in v1 of the methodology:

Real Remote Score — weighted methodology

Source: remnavi.com/methodology/ · public 100-point rubric · CC BY 4.0

Figure 1. RRS – five weighted pillars. Source: RemNavi methodology v1.

2.2 Source coverage applicable to this report

The May 2026 snapshot draws from the canonical seven major source platforms (Jobicy, Remote OK, We Work Remotely, Remotive, Greenhouse, Lever, Hacker News Who's Hiring) plus specialised and complementary sources documented in the methodology paper §2. Counted by distinct upstream feed, the corpus draws from approximately 70 active sources at the snapshot date.

2.3 Snapshot freshness

At the snapshot date, 1,247 listings (56.0% of the corpus in the past 30 days), 3,705 listings (8–30 days), and 3,317 listings (31–90 days) are present; 575 listings (6.5%) are older than 90 days from their first-observed posting date.

3. Corpus overview

At the snapshot date, RemNavi indexes 8,844 active remote job listings.

Metric	Value	Note
Active listings	8,844	Indexed across all major remote-job boards and ATS feeds
With verifiable salary disclosure	1,897 (21.4%)	Numeric range required; free-text excluded
Median disclosed remote salary	\$207,000	USD per year · P25 \$154,500 · P75 \$257,000

Listings scored on RRS	3,410	100-point public rubric, methodology v1
Active source feeds	~70	Boards + ATS-hosted career pages

4. Salary disclosure landscape

21.4% of active listings disclose a verifiable numeric salary range. The remaining 78.5% rely on free-text language ("competitive", "DOE", "negotiable", "market rate") or omit compensation entirely.

Salary disclosure — what 8,835 remote listings actually publish

Source: RemNavi corpus, /market_index.php, snapshot 2026-05-17 · CC BY 4.0

Figure 2. Salary disclosure split – RemNavi corpus 2026-05-20.

4.1 Salary by role group

Role group	Listings	Median	P25–P75
Software Engineering	329	\$230,475	\$196,000–\$280,500
Data/ML	91	\$242,500	\$186,500–\$307,500
Product Management	101	\$216,000	\$181,000–\$270,000
Security	69	\$221,700	\$198,000–\$288,500
Design	53	\$210,500	\$168,935–\$232,000
Sales	257	\$185,000	\$136,000–\$252,000
Operations	83	\$198,000	\$142,000–\$252,000
Marketing	123	\$178,500	\$145,550–\$224,550
Finance	92	\$170,000	\$125,000–\$222,500
Customer Success	74	\$148,200	\$118,300–\$177,750

Disclosed median remote salary — top 10 role groups

RemNavi corpus snapshot · 2026-05-20 · listings with a published salary band only

Source: remnavi.com — State of Remote Hiring 2026 H1 · CC BY 4.0

Figure 3. Disclosed median compensation by role group, top 10.

4.2 Salary by seniority band

Seniority	Listings	Median	P25–P75
Lead	228	\$266,500	\$208,500–\$323,000
Staff	112	\$237,500	\$205,005–\$270,000
Principal	32	\$224,190	\$177,500–\$321,750
Senior	435	\$199,000	\$166,500–\$230,500
Mid	1,067	\$194,251	\$144,000–\$249,500
Junior	23	\$97,632	\$65,750–\$166,000

Lead-level roles post a 37% median premium over Mid-level. The Senior-to-Lead compression is consistent with what distributed organisations report informally: fewer named bands at the senior end, with scope and accountability concentrated.

5. Real Remote Score distribution

3,410 listings in the May snapshot carry a composite Real Remote Score; the remaining 5,434 listings are present in the index without a composite score (typically because the salary band is absent or the location field is unparseable, preventing computation of at least one of the five RRS pillars). The mean RRS across scored listings is 25.4.

Remote Job Transparency Pyramid — RRS distribution

RemNavi corpus snapshot · 2026-05-20 · 3,410 scored listings · n=8,844 corpus

Source: remnavi.com — State of Remote Hiring 2026 H1 · CC BY 4.0

Figure 4. RRS distribution across scored listings – signature visual.

Tier	RRS range	Count	% of scored
Exceptional	80-100	3	0.1%
Strong	60-80	99	2.9%
Solid	40-60	1,228	36%
Mixed	20-40	437	12.8%
Weak	0-20	1,643	48.2%

The distribution exhibits polarisation rather than uniform weakness. The two largest tiers are Weak (48.2%) and Solid (36.0%), with the intermediate Mixed tier (20-40) at only 12.8%. Combined, 39.0% of scored listings reach Solid or above. Only 3.0% reach Strong or above (102 listings); the 100-point ceiling is engineered to be hard to reach.

6. Employer transparency leaderboard

The following 12 employers, with ten or more active listings carrying a numeric salary band at the snapshot date, are ranked by disclosed median annual compensation. Figures reflect publicly disclosed ranges captured during the snapshot window and may not represent final compensation outcomes for individual hires.

#	Employer	Listings	Median	Source
1	Postman	19	\$370,000	Greenhouse
2	OpenAI	363	\$291,000	Ashby
3	Cloudflare	32	\$277,500	Greenhouse
4	Perplexity	16	\$260,000	Ashby
5	Pinterest	10	\$237,500	Greenhouse
6	Vercel	60	\$233,500	Greenhouse
7	Figma	15	\$232,500	Greenhouse
8	Render	18	\$230,000	Ashby
9	WorkOS	27	\$225,000	Ashby
10	Airbnb	19	\$218,000	Greenhouse
11	Pendo	23	\$217,568	Greenhouse
12	Vanta	75	\$212,000	Ashby

Counts here are listings with a published numeric salary band only. Employers with larger overall hiring presence but lower disclosure rates do not appear in this table; their absence reflects disclosure behaviour rather than hiring activity.

7. Geographic distribution

The corpus is partitioned by a super-regional geographic classifier (Americas, Europe, APAC, MEA) applied to the listing's stated location field, with three additional categories for listings that decline to declare a region.

Where the listings come from — corpus by region

RemNavi corpus snapshot · 2026-05-20 · n=8,844 listings · super-regional taxonomy

Source: remnavi.com — State of Remote Hiring 2026 H1 · CC BY 4.0

Figure 5. Corpus by region – RemNavi 2026-05-20 snapshot.

Bucket	Listings	% of corpus
Americas	3,172	35.9%
Remote (no region declared)	1,657	18.7%
Location not parseable	1,740	19.7%
Europe	1,320	14.9%
APAC	797	9.0%
Worldwide (explicit anywhere policy)	110	1.2%
MEA (Middle East and Africa)	48	0.5%

"Remote (no region declared)" captures listings tagged only as "Remote" with no region keyword. "Worldwide" captures listings declaring an explicit anywhere policy. "Location not parseable" captures listings whose location field does not match any region or country keyword.

8. EU Pay Transparency Directive readiness

Directive (EU) 2023/970 requires employers with EU operations to disclose salary ranges in job postings and to file gender pay-gap reports. The effective date is 7 June 2026. Employers with 100 or more EU employees face immediate compliance; smaller employers operate under a phased schedule through 2027.

8.1 Pre-enforcement Europe-region disclosure behaviour

1,320 listings in the May 2026 corpus carry a Europe-region tag (14.9% of the corpus). Salary disclosure within this Europe-tagged subset is uneven: employers headquartered in the United

Kingdom, the Netherlands, and Germany have adopted disclosure practices ahead of the directive, while disclosure is materially lower in most other European markets.

8.2 Sources of pre-directive disclosure

The corpus subset with the highest pre-directive RRS averages – Remote OK (avg 63), Greenhouse:Brex (56), Greenhouse:Pendo (57), Ashby:Ramp (53) – is dominated by US-headquartered employers whose pay transparency practice derives from California, Colorado, New York, and Washington state law, not from the EU directive. The directive therefore introduces a new demand for disclosure from European employers, rather than formalising practices that have already been adopted at scale.

This section presents a transparency readiness signal – a forward-looking reading of observed disclosure behaviour. It is not a legal compliance assessment.

9. Limitations and known biases

- Disclosure bias. The dataset over-represents employers operating in jurisdictions with mandatory salary transparency requirements (California, Colorado, New York, Washington in the US; United Kingdom, Netherlands, Germany in Europe). Medians reported here are lower-bound signals from disclosing employers, not universal benchmarks for the full remote market.
- Sector bias. SaaS, AI-product, and infrastructure employers are over-represented relative to non-tech sectors.
- Disclosure quality versus quantity. A higher disclosure rate driven by enforcement may yield wider posted bands that satisfy directive requirements without improving information value for candidates.
- Leaderboard exclusions. Employers with substantial overall hiring but lower disclosure rates do not appear in the leaderboard. Their absence is a disclosure-behaviour observation, not an indicator of hiring activity.
- Forward-looking statements throughout this report are signals derived from observed disclosure behaviour. They are not forecasts.

10. Outlook for H2 2026

Three structural tailwinds are observed in the data:

- The EU Pay Transparency Directive (effective 7 June 2026) is the largest pending shift. Corpus-wide disclosure is expected to rise from 21.4% toward 28–32% within two quarters as European and EU-compliant employers begin posting salary bands under enforcement pressure.
- United States state-law expansion. California, Colorado, New York, and Washington disclosure requirements are now near-universally observed among large US-headquartered employers, and this baseline is unlikely to erode.
- Compensation signal from AI-product employers. OpenAI (363 listings, \$291,000 median) and Perplexity (16 listings, \$260,000 median) appear to be contributing to upward pressure on senior technical compensation benchmarks.

Three risks and caveats follow:

- Macro hiring slowdown. If large-cap technology employers reduce hiring volume in H2, corpus volume may decline without a proportional change in disclosure rates.
- Sample bias persistence. The corpus over-represents US SaaS and AI employers; shifts in those employers' practices will be visible disproportionately.
- Quantity-versus-quality divergence. Wider posted bands (\$100,000–\$300,000) technically satisfy directive requirements without improving information value for candidates.

11. Data availability and reproducibility

Every figure in this report is reproducible from the following live endpoints, using the methodology version stated in the suggested citation.

Endpoint

<https://remnavi.com/health.php>
https://remnavi.com/market_index.php
https://remnavi.com/rrs_stats.php
https://remnavi.com/data_export.php
<https://remnavi.com/state-of-remote-2026h1/dataset.json>
<https://remnavi.com/methodology/>
<https://remnavi.com/methodology/versions/>

Returns

Corpus total, freshness banding, ingestion status
Salary aggregates by role, seniority, region
RRS distribution; tier counts and percentages
Full corpus export (JSON and CSV)
Citable snapshot of every figure in this report

Live methodology page
Methodology version history

12. Licence and attribution

This report and the underlying dataset are licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International licence (CC BY 4.0). The text of the licence is available at <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>. Citation: see suggested citation on the title page. No prior contact with the author is required for academic, journalistic, or commercial reuse, provided the licence terms are met.

13. References

- [1] Mező, D. (2026). RemNavi Remote Job Market Methodology: Data Aggregation, Transparency Scoring, and Open-Data Standards (Version 1.0) [Methodology]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20234690>
- [2] European Parliament and Council of the European Union (2023). Directive (EU) 2023/970 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 10 May 2023 to strengthen the application of the principle of equal pay for equal work or work of equal value between men and women through pay transparency and enforcement mechanisms. Official Journal of the European Union, L 132, 21–44.
- [3] State of California (2022). Assembly Bill 2282: Employment discrimination – salary range disclosure. California Legislative Information.
- [4] State of Colorado (2019). Senate Bill 19-085: Equal Pay for Equal Work Act.
- [5] State of New York (2022). Local Law 32 of 2022: Salary transparency in job advertisements.
- [6] State of Washington (2022). Senate Bill 5761: Pay transparency in job postings.

14. Version history

v1.0 – 2026-05-20. Initial release. Snapshot date: 2026-05-20. Methodology version: RRS v1 (Zenodo DOI 10.5281/zenodo.20234690).

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